

Knowledge Systems in the Blue Economy

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Introduction

Access to technology, information and knowledge affects global competition, wealth and power. It also exacerbates inequality where communities have a limited ability to generate information; or where knowledge governance is hindered by social, cultural, political, economic and institutional factors, structures and processes (Alff & Hornidge, 2019; Quéau, 2002; van Kerkhoff, 2014). These established global knowledge governance structures enable social hierarchies that proliferate through global environmental governance forums and practices (Niner et al., 2024).

Processes within global environmental governance forums require information and knowledge that facilitate discourse aimed at progressing development agendas and related priorities. These processes require the engagement of diverse groups of stakeholders from multiple nations, and take place within a limited timeframe. Globalized knowledge generalizes world views and experiences, and the processes of knowledge generation become detached from the ways in which knowledge has been made meaningful (Jasanoff, 2010; Turnhout et al., 2016). This is particularly evident in the global standardization of biodiversity knowledge that has been contributed from a diverse range of local systems that have differing ways of knowing and living with nature (Turnhout et al., 2016). Globalized knowledge can erase geographical and cultural differences, encompassing decontextualized views that are detached from the ways that knowledge and policy are made meaningful (Hulme, 2010; Jasanoff, 2010; Turnhout et al., 2016); and it can also promote the interests of local elites (Raymond et al., 2010). Developing knowledge generation and management processes and products that support more authentic engagement requires innovation, capacity, infrastructure, and resources. These can be inherently challenging to coordinate in least developed countries and Small Island Developing States (SIDS).

The blue economy is a global and loosely defined concept that emerged out of the 2012 United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (or Rio+20) preparation meetings (IISD, 2011; Silver et al., 2015). The blue economy is founded on principles of sustainability. Sustainability is complex and intertwined, embracing cultural, social, ecological, environmental, economic, and political factors (Hoareau, 2023). The advancement of a blue economy is influenced by the extent to which the local community and context are intertwined in blue economy-related development plans and frameworks (Niner et al., 2022). The local knowledge system influences the quality of communication, implementation, decision-making, and adaptive management and has the potential to enable impactful local engagement in a more sustainable blue economy, allowing local

communities to advocate for their priorities at global governance level (Hoareau, 2023). This paper explores the links between knowledge systems and global environmental governance, in relation to advancing a more sustainable blue economy, by highlighting the local knowledge system in Seychelles, a country recognized as one of the early leaders in the blue economy space.

Background

Global environmental governance is characterized by a complex mix of dynamic challenges; with new knowledge constantly emerging to shape learning, decision-making implementation and adaptive management (Fazey et al., 2013; Gerlak et al., 2020). The process of knowledge exchange is usually seen as a tool rather than a complex and diverse social and structural system (Fazey et al., 2013). Questions of ontology define the knowledge and power dynamics that influence global environmental governance and sustainability approaches i.e., how these are envisioned, designed, and enacted (Fisher et al., 2022; Raymond et al., 2010). Western-orientated ontologies usually shape the actions that take place at global environmental governance level, diluting the relevance of local and indigenous ontologies in governance processes (Campion et al., 2023; DePuy et al., 2022; Fisher et al., 2022). These governance mechanisms have proven to be unable to engage diverse ontologies (DePuy et al., 2022) that embrace different ways of relating to and engaging with the coastal and ocean space.

Various institutional mechanisms have been developed to govern and protect marine and coastal areas, and these mechanisms require a level of simplification and generalization, often losing local context and meaning in the process (Fisher et al., 2022). Integrating scientific and local knowledge into environmental governance and management can facilitate more contextualized knowledge that can enable a more grounded understanding of the problem, with stronger ownership and advancement of effective solutions (Taylor & de Loë, 2012). Various initiatives and programmes are actively engaging targets and goals that facilitate the integration of local and indigenous knowledge; for example the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), the Ocean Decade 2030, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, etc. Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches to studying complex global problems have helped integrate diverse ways of knowing and doing, but these require time, capacity, funding, and a diverse combination of skills to support the development and life cycle of such projects and collaboration (Greenhill et al., 2015).

Knowledge and knowledge systems

Mobilizing science and technology are seen as key components of meeting human development needs and promoting sustainable development (Cash et al., 2003).

Conflicting epistemologies influence scientific debates in environmental governance forums and how science and knowledge are dealt with and understood in negotiations (De Donà, 2023; Taylor & de Loë, 2012). Scientific knowledge has played a central role in framing global sustainability problems and influencing societal responses to these problems (Cornell et al., 2013; Taylor & de Loë, 2012). This continues to influence research investment and scientific effort undertaken by established knowledge systems and institutions worldwide (Cornell et al., 2013). What it means to know something and the nature of this knowledge are epistemological questions that have been debated by many (Nickols, 2013).

Put simply, Nickols (2013) describes knowledge as state of knowing. He captures the core categories as: what we know about something (and how we acquire this); how we apply what we know (the capacity for action); and how we capture what we know (the body of knowledge or knowledge artifacts, inclusive of information and data that exist apart from people). He quotes this definition captured by Davenport and Prusak (1998):

Knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. It originates and is applied in the minds of knowers. In organizations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories but also in organizational routines, processes, practices, and norms.

Cornell et al. (2013) note that knowledge systems are made up of diverse groups of agents, practices, institutions, and networks that play a significant role in the production, transfer and use of knowledge. In relation to sustainability, they quote van Kerkhoff and Szlezák (2016) who define a knowledge system as being:

...a network of actors connected by social relationships, formal or informal, that dynamically combine knowing, doing, and learning to bring about specific actions for sustainable development.

Various authors have noted that established knowledge systems are inadequate for guiding any major societal transformation needed to address the complex environmental and social challenges that influence sustainable development (Arnott & Lemos, 2021; Cornell et al., 2013; Fazey et al., 2020; Kläy et al., 2015; Oliver et al., 2021; van Kerkhoff & Szlezák, 2016).

There is a dynamic relationship between the tangible (e.g., structures, processes, technology, finance) and the less tangible (e.g., experience, values, priorities) factors that influence what knowledge exists and how it is utilized within programmes, institutions, organizations, governance forums and local communities. This is made even more complicated when considering diverse social and cultural contexts. Flexible and adaptive institutions are being recognized as playing a key role in action and implementation, with

institutions that deal with sustainable development being challenged by new forms of collaboration and partnership that link local knowledge with innovative action (van Kerkhoff & Szlezák, 2016). Transdisciplinary approaches that engage academics from different disciplines with non-academic actors, to coproduce knowledge that addresses complex contemporary challenges, are evolving to enable more innovative approaches to promoting sustainable development.

The blue economy and knowledge systems

The blue economy gained prominence when island nations related their vast blue space to concepts being discussed in global green economy discourse (see Figure 1). They recognized that the ocean was an important sustainable development space for their nations, and many island nations like Seychelles have advanced their own blue economy agendas since.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the Green Economy Index (based on principles of sustainable development) and the link to the blue economy

(Image credit: Global Green Growth Institute, in Rijsberman et al., 2020)

A sustainable ocean economy (or blue economy) refers to the coastal and ocean-based activities that directly and indirectly contribute to the prosperity of a country (Hoareau, 2023). The operationalization of a blue economy at a local level is largely influenced by international commitments, funding (Sumaila et al., 2022) and engagement, with key organizations (such as the World Bank, the United Nations, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the European Union, the High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, the World Wildlife Fund for Nature and various

others) influencing the direction of development and investment. Engagement in global governance forums and agendas is influenced by multiple factors, but the local knowledge system can influence the power dynamics and how inclusive engagement takes place when negotiating global agreements and instruments that relate to the blue economy. These systems can also influence which commitments and investment opportunities are pursued, and how they are enacted (or not) locally. This also brings about tension when local needs and priorities are compromised and sacrificed to accommodate what is perceived as international best practice in global environmental governance arenas where international negotiations take place (Bennett et al., 2019; Niner et al., 2024).

The diverse groups of stakeholders and sectors that make up the blue economy require knowledge systems and processes that are impactful at multiple levels, engaging diverse values and world views. At a local level, the effectiveness of the knowledge systems and infrastructure can empower or disempower multiple stakeholders or drive the local agenda in a direction that benefits some and not others. Accessible technology, information and knowledge promote a more equitable engagement that is based on a more sustainable and integrated approach, but they can also bring about their own biases and interpretations when the local context and relevance to this is considered.

For SIDS like Seychelles, international engagement provides vital funding and knowledge needed to drive local sustainability agendas like the blue economy. International expectations and funder requirements can hold practitioners accountable to their agreed commitments (particularly if they intend to target more international funding), but this has the potential to dilute local agendas and priorities if these differ from those laid out by countries whose priorities are led by western-orientated ontologies.

The knowledge system's influence on the blue economy in Seychelles

The knowledge production and exchange landscape in Seychelles is dynamic and complex. Although Seychelles has a Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (2016-2025), there is currently no national research strategy aimed at supporting sustainable development and related policy needs. Local efforts are underway to develop the framework for a national marine research agenda that aims to determine research priorities and capacity development needs with the aim of developing a management-oriented national marine research agenda¹.

Various departments and organizations (public, private, non-governmental and not-for-profit) undertake research that aligns with local (and usually internationally relevant)

¹ DEVELOPMENT OF A SEYCHELLES NATIONAL MARINE RESEARCH AGENDA ([google.com](https://unisey.ac.sc/news/survey-national-research-agenda-for-sustainable-ocean-development/)); and <https://unisey.ac.sc/news/survey-national-research-agenda-for-sustainable-ocean-development/>

environmental governance and management priorities, but this is usually driven by their own research priorities and strategies. Many local organizations collaborate with international consultants, researchers, institutes, and organizations. Collaborative ocean expedition research, for example those lead by the Nekton Foundation, The Monaco Exploration Society, Ocean X, etc., has played an important role in attracting innovative exploration and research technology to Seychelles. It has also supported local scientific and ocean expedition-related capacity development. International collaboration plays a vital role in advancing research needs and benchmarking action against international best-practice, but this practice also means that local issues and challenges can be diluted to fit with generic western-orientated standards and expectations when no local research strategy is present. This informal knowledge system can broaden the gap as researchers and organizations (local and international) advance their own research with limited accountability and formal knowledge exchange pathways.

Various enabling mechanisms support the development of a sustainable and integrated approach to advancing a local blue economy framework, and knowledge systems are at the heart of this (see Hoareau (2023) for more details). My research aims to evaluate the influence of the local knowledge system in Seychelles on the blue economy by:

- ◆ highlighting the relationship between the blue economy and local knowledge systems to empower cross-sectoral engagement and collaboration that advances sustainability;
- ◆ determining which aspects of the local knowledge system support (or are a barrier to) empowered decision-making, adaptive management, and effective policy development;
- ◆ demonstrating mechanisms and processes that empower cross-sectoral engagement, critical thinking, and innovative collaboration to improve knowledge co-production.

The research has been designed to capture the views of key informants across knowledge categories (see Figure 2) with questions designed to draw out institutional mechanisms and practices, as well as social and cultural factors that are important for a locally relevant and functional knowledge systems.

Figure 2: The knowledge system framed in the context of this research
 (Image influenced by Hertz et al., 2020; and Oliver et al., 2021)

Conclusion

The importance of knowledge in environmental governance and sustainable development negotiations, forums, programmes and initiatives is well recognized; but knowledge production, exchange and uptake processes remain entrenched in embedded and western-orientated approaches.

Part of this challenge can be addressed by creating impactful local knowledge systems that can empower broader engagement and collaboration, and that are fit for purpose. Local knowledge is built through knowledge system that are culturally sensitive and embedded within local communities. This may or may not reflect the norms and practices that have evolved in global governance forums led and dominated by western-orientated knowledge systems and processes. These local knowledge systems can facilitate impactful local and international collaboration that supports the advancement of, and investment in, local priorities identified in sustainable development frameworks like the blue economy. This also strengthens knowledge exchange pathways and allows for local knowledge to be built on and developed over time. A formal local knowledge system allows local communities to be engaged in national sustainable development priorities, and ensures that these are embedded locally, regardless of capacity and government changes that might occur and disrupt plans and progress.

Seychelles has the foundational components needed to create a strong local knowledge system, but there needs to be a clearer understanding of the tangible and intangible parts of the system, and the relationship between them, to empower long-lasting and impactful

knowledge production, exchange, and uptake that has a real impact on progressing an authentically sustainable blue economy.

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References

- Alff, H. and Hornidge, A.-K. (2019). 'Transformation' in International Development Studies: Across Disciplines, Knowledge Hierarchies and Oceanic Spaces'. In *Building Development Studies for the New Millennium*, I. Baud, E. Basile, T. Kontinen and S. von Itter (eds.), pp.141-161. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04052-9_7
- Arnott, J.C. and Lemos, M.C. (2021). 'Understanding knowledge use for sustainability'. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 120, pp.222-230. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.02.016>
- Bennett, N.J., Cisneros-Montemayor, A.M., Blythe, J., Silver, J.J., Singh, G., Andrews, N., Calò, A., Christie, P., Di Franco, A., Finkbeiner, E.M., Gelcich, S., Guidetti, P., Harper, S., Hotte, N., Kittinger, J.N., Le Billon, P., Lister, J., López de la Lama, R., McKinley, E., . . . Sumaila, U.R. (2019). 'Towards a sustainable and equitable blue economy'. *Nature Sustainability*, 2 (11), pp.991-993. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0404-1>
- Campion, O.B., West, S., Degnien, K., Djarrbal, M., Ignjic, E., Ramandjarri, C., Malibirr, G. W., Guwankil, M., Djigirr, P. and Biridjala, F. (2023). 'Balpara: A practical approach to working with ontological difference in indigenous land and sea management'. *Society and Natural Resources*, 37 (5).
- Cash, D.W., Clark, W.C., Alcock, F., Dickson, N.M., Eckley, N., Guston, D.H., Jäger, J. and Mitchell, R.B. (2003). 'Knowledge systems for sustainable development'. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 100 (14), 8086-8091.
- Cornell, S., Berkhout, F., Tuinstra, W., Tàbara, J.D., Jäger, J., Chabay, I., de Wit, B., Langlais, R., Mills, D., Moll, P., Otto, I.M., Petersen, A., Pohl, C. and van Kerkhoff, L. (2013). 'Opening up Knowledge Systems for Better Responses to Global Environmental Change'. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 28, pp.60-70. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.11.008>
- Davenport, T.H. and Prusak, L. (1998). *Working Knowledge: How organizations manage what they know*. Harvard Business Press.
- De Donà, M. (2023). 'Is it only about science and policy? The 'intergovernmental epistemologies' of global environmental governance'. *Journal of International Relations and Development*, 26 (1), pp.86-110. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41268-022-00276-w>
- DePuy, W., Weger, J., Foster, K., Bonanno, A.M., Kumar, S., Lear, K., Basilio, R. and German, L. (2022). 'Environmental Governance: Broadening ontological spaces for a more livable world'. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 5 (2), pp.947-975. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25148486211018565>
- Fazey, I., Evely, A.C., Reed, M.S., Stringer, L.C., Kruijssen, J., White, P.C.L., Newsham, A., Jin, L., Cortazzi, M., Phillipson, J., Blackstock, K., Entwistle, N., Sheate, W., Armstrong, F., Blackmore, C., Fazey, J., Ingram, J., Gregson, J.O.N., Lowe, P., . . . Trevitt, C. (2013). 'Knowledge Exchange: A review and research agenda for environmental management'. *Environmental Conservation*, 40 (1), pp.19-36. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S037689291200029X>

- Fazey, I., Schöpke, N., Caniglia, G., Hodgson, A., Kendrick, I., Lyon, C., Page, G., Patterson, J., Riedy, C., Strasser, T., Verveen, S., Adams, D., Goldstein, B., Klaes, M., Leicester, G., Linyard, A., McCurdy, A., Ryan, P., Sharpe, B., . . . Young, H.R. (2020). 'Transforming knowledge systems for life on Earth: Visions of future systems and how to get there'. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 70, 101724. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101724>
- Fisher, K., Makey, L., Macpherson, E., Paul, A., Rennie, H., Talbot-Jones, J. and Jorgensen, E. (2022). 'Broadening environmental governance ontologies to enhance ecosystem-based management in Aotearoa New Zealand'. *Maritime Studies*, 21 (4), pp.609-629. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40152-022-00278-x>
- Gerlak, A.K., Heikkilä, T. and Newig, J. (2020). 'Learning in environmental governance: opportunities for translating theory to practice'. *Journal of Environmental Policy and Planning*, 22 (5), pp.653-666. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2020.1776100>
- Greenhill, L., Hughes, A., Day, J. and Stanley, M. (2015). 'Blue Knowledge - Developing knowledge to support transition to a Blue Economy: A strategic approach'. *Island Studies Journal*, 3, pp.6-10.
- Hertz, J.C., Brinkerhoff, D.W., Bush, R. and Karetji, P. (2020). *Knowledge systems: Evidence to policy concepts in practice*.
- Hoareau, K. (2023). 'The blue economy: Who knows what?' In *Annual Report on Global Islands 2022*, J.N. Telesford (ed.), pp.57-77. Island Studies Press. <https://islandstudies.com/research/annual-report-on-global-islands/annual-report-on-global-islands-2022/>
- Hulme, M. (2010). 'Problems with making and governing global kinds of knowledge'. *Global Environmental Change*, 20 (4), pp.558-564. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.07.005>
- IISD (2011). Delegates Call for Attention to the 'Blue Economy' at UNCSD PrepCom II. <http://sdg.iisd.org/news/delegates-call-for-attention-to-the-blue-economy-at-uncsd-prepcom-ii/> [Retrieved 2 Jan 2023].
- Jasanoff, S. (2010). 'A new climate for society'. *Theory, culture and society*, 27 (2-3), pp.233-253.
- Kläy, A., Zimmermann, A.B. and Schneider, F. (2015). 'Rethinking science for sustainable development: Reflexive interaction for a paradigm transformation'. *Futures*, 65, pp.72-85. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2014.10.012>
- Nickols, F. (2013). 'The tacit and explicit nature of knowledge: The knowledge in knowledge management'. In *The knowledge management yearbook 2000-2001*, pp.12-21. Routledge.
- Niner, H.J., Barut, N.C., Baum, T., Diz, D., del Pozo, D.L., Laing, S., Lancaster, A.M.S., McQuaid, K.A., Mendo, T. and Morgera, E. (2022). 'Issues of context, capacity and scale: Essential conditions and missing links for a sustainable blue economy'. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 130, pp.25-35.
- Niner, H.J., Wilson, D., Hoareau, K., Strand, M., Whittingham, J., McGarry, D., Erinosho, B., Ibrahim, S., Tshiningayamwe, S., Febrica, S., Lancaster, A.M.S.N. and Prokic, M. (2024). 'Reflections on the past, present, and potential futures of knowledge hierarchies in ocean biodiversity governance research' [Policy and Practice Reviews]. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2024.1347494>
- Oliver, T.H., Benini, L., Borja, A., Dupont, C., Doherty, B., Grodzińska-Jurczak, M., Iglesias, A., Jordan, A., Kass, G., Lung, T., Maguire, C., McGonigle, D., Mickwitz, P., Spangenberg, J.H. and Tarrason, L. (2021). 'Knowledge architecture for the wise governance of sustainability transitions'. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 126, pp.152-163. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.09.025>
- Quéau, P. (2002). 'Global Governance and Knowledge Societies'. *Development*, 45 (4), pp.10-16. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.development.1110398>
- Raymond, C.M., Fazey, I., Reed, M.S., Stringer, L.C., Robinson, G.M. and Evely, A.C. (2010). 'Integrating local and scientific knowledge for environmental management'. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 91 (8), pp.1766-1777. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.03.023>

- Rijsberman, F., Acosta, L., Bhardwaj, N., Dickinson, C., Gibson, M., Grafakos, S., Solvang, I. and Storey, D. (2020). *Achieving Green Growth and Climate Action Post-COVID-19*.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13208.42240>
- Silver, J.J., Gray, N.J., Campbell, L.M., Fairbanks, L.W. and Gruby, R.L. (2015). 'Blue Economy and Competing Discourses in International Oceans Governance'. *The Journal of Environment and Development*, 24 (2), pp.135-160. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1070496515580797>
- Sumaila, U.R., Walsh, M., Hoareau, K., Cox, A., Teh, L., Abdallah, P., Akpalu, W., Anna, Z., Benzaken, D., Crona, B., Fitzgerald, T., Heaps, L., Issifu, I., Karousakis, K., Lange, G.M., Leland, A., Miller, D., Sack, K., Shahnaz, D., . . . Zhang, J. (2022). 'Financing a sustainable ocean economy'. *Nature Communications*, 13 (1), p.1756. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29418-x>
- Taylor, B. and de Loë, R. C. (2012). 'Conceptualizations of local knowledge in collaborative environmental governance'. *Geoforum*, 43 (6), pp.1207-1217.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2012.03.007>
- Turnhout, E., Dewulf, A. and Hulme, M. (2016). 'What does policy-relevant global environmental knowledge do? The cases of climate and biodiversity'. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 18, pp.65-72. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.09.004>
- van Kerkhoff, L. (2014). *Knowledge Governance for Sustainable Development: A Review (Vol. 1)* [global public goods; innovation; knowledge governance; knowledge systems; sustainable development].
<http://www.librelloph.com/challengesinsustainability/article/view/cis-1-2-82>
- van Kerkhoff, L. and Szlezák, N.A. (2016). 'The role of innovative global institutions in linking knowledge and action'. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 113 (17), pp.4603-4608.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.0900541107>

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